

The Biotechnological Potential and Treatment Processes of Cheese Whey

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Abstract

The global rise in dairy product consumption has significantly increased the volume of waste generated by the dairy industry, particularly cheese whey (CW), a by-product rich in organic matter and bioactive compounds. Owing to its high chemical and biological oxygen demand, the untreated discharge of CW poses serious environmental threats. However, its rich composition, which includes proteins, lactose, and minerals, makes whey a promising raw material for environmental management as well as for the production of value-added products. This review offers a comprehensive evaluation of the biotechnological potential of whey and the treatment technologies applied since 2004. Emphasis is placed on anaerobic processes and membrane-based separation techniques, and novel integrated approaches aimed at promoting circular economy principles. The study highlights recent advances in resource recovery, biogas generation, and bioactive compound isolation, while addressing the ecological and economic implications of whey valorization through sustainable and innovative methods.

Keywords: Cheese whey, biotechnological valorization, anaerobic digestion, membrane technologies

1. Introduction

There has been a consistent rise in the worldwide demand for milk and its derived products in recent years. In parallel with this rise, efforts to develop new products containing prebiotic and probiotic components known for their beneficial effects on human health have also become more widespread (Pires et al., 2021). In 2010, Europe became the largest exporter of dairy products worldwide, with dairy accounting for approximately 13% of the total turnover of the European Union (EU) food and beverage sector (Valta et al., 2015). In 2014, farms in the EU-28 countries produced approximately 164.8 million tons of milk in total, of which 68.8 million tons were used in the production of 5.5 million tons of cheese (Valta et al., 2017). According to the most recent data, raw milk production in the European Union reached approximately 160.8 million tons in 2023. Cow's milk constituted 96% of this production, while the remainder came from sheep, goat, and buffalo milk (Eurostat, 2024). Cow's milk plays a fundamental role in human nutrition due to its high nutritional value and versatile applications. In addition to being consumed directly, milk is also processed into a wide range of dairy products such as yogurt, cheese, milk powder, fermented products, and cream-based items (O'Mahony and Fox, 2014). Among the sectors generating waste and wastewater, the dairy industry an integral part of the European Union economy represents one of the most promising fields for biorefinery applications (Asunis et al., 2020). The increasing scale of cheese production has led to a corresponding rise in waste generation from the dairy sector (Luján-Facundo et al., 2017). The dairy industry stands out as one of the leading subsectors in the food industry in terms of liquid waste production (Mirabella et al., 2014). Cheese manufacturing generates three main waste streams: cheese whey (CW), secondary cheese whey (originating respectively from cheese and ricotta/cottage cheese production), and dairy wastewater from equipment and tank cleaning operations (Asunis et al., 2020). In cheese production, approximately 10% of the milk input is

converted into cheese, while the remaining 90% becomes a liquid by-product known as "whey" (Valta et al., 2015). It is estimated that 9–10 liters of cheese whey are produced per kilogram of cheese (Pires et al., 2021), and its widespread generation leads to the global formation of approximately 400 billion liters of wastewater annually (Asunis et al., 2020). Cheese whey (CW) typically contains a significant amount of organic matter, with volatile solids (VS) ranging from 45 to 65 g kg⁻¹ and chemical oxygen demand (COD) levels reported between 68 and 94 g l⁻¹ (Escalante et al., 2018). The biological oxygen demand (BOD) ranges from 27 to 60 g l⁻¹, with more than 90% of this load attributed to lactose (Carvalho et al., 2013). The uncontrolled discharge of whey with such a high pollutant load into the environment without adequate treatment poses a significant threat to ecosystems. Therefore, various treatment methods are commonly employed for the management of high-organic-content CW, including thermocatalytic treatment (Remón et al., 2016), anaerobic digestion (Asunis et al., 2020), electrocoagulation (Tirado et al., 2018), and membrane processes (Blais et al., 2022; Pires et al., 2021; Mansor et al., 2021). Additionally, membrane processes such as reverse osmosis, nanofiltration (NF), ultrafiltration (UF), and microfiltration (MF) are also utilized for the recovery and production of valuable compounds like proteins and lactose (Talebi et al., 2020). Whey is considered a highly valuable by-product due to its richness in proteins, lactose, and minerals such as calcium, magnesium, and phosphorus, making its recovery and valorization highly significant (Yorgun et al., 2008). Whey proteins play crucial roles in various technological functions, including emulsification, foaming, and gel formation (Madureira et al., 2007). Owing to their protein structure, which closely resembles that of human milk, whey proteins are commonly used in medical and dietary products such as infant formulas. Furthermore, due to their content of bioactive peptides, whey proteins can exhibit immunomodulatory, antioxidant, antimicrobial, and antihypertensive effects

(Smithers, 2008). Various methods such as ultrafiltration (UF), diafiltration (DF), nanofiltration (NF), ion-exchange chromatography, electrophoresis, crystallization, and precipitation are utilized to isolate and concentrate whey proteins from accompanying constituents (Pires et al., 2021). These techniques are not only used to isolate the major proteins but are also effective in obtaining trace bioactive compounds and peptides (Pihlanto, 2011). In this context, whey should not be regarded merely as an environmental waste, but rather as a valuable bioresource that enables the recovery of high value-added compounds. Processing whey through appropriate biotechnological methods is of great importance for both ensuring ecological sustainability and enhancing economic benefit. This study provides a comprehensive overview of the biotechnological potential of whey and the treatment technologies employed from 2005 to the present, with a particular focus on sustainable and innovative approaches. It aims to evaluate the current state of research and identify prospective advancements through an integrated, environmentally conscious lens.

2. Whey treatment methods

High concentrations of pollutants including ammonium nitrogen, total phosphorus, chemical oxygen demand (COD), and biological oxygen demand (BOD) are commonly found in wastewaters derived from cheese processing operations, such as CW, SCW, and cleaning effluents (Kotoulas et al., 2019). The direct discharge of whey into water bodies or soil leads to eutrophication in aquatic ecosystems by depleting dissolved oxygen levels and negatively impacts microbial balance (Prazeres et al., 2012). Moreover, the high organic load increases toxicity risk, posing significant environmental threats. In this context, the implementation of effective treatment systems through sustainable approaches is of great importance to mitigate the adverse environmental impacts of whey.

The high organic content of cheese whey (CW) necessitates the development of diverse treatment strategies, both to reduce environmental harm and to capitalize on potential economic gains. For the treatment of such agro-industrial wastewater, various technologies are employed, including physicochemical or biological systems, electrochemical methods, constructed wetlands, advanced oxidation processes, membrane technologies, or hybrid systems combining these approaches (Demirel, 2015; Valta et al., 2017; Tirado et al., 2018; Kotoulas et al., 2019; Talebi et al., 2020).

2.1. Anaerobic treatment methods

According to the literature on the treatment and valorization of cheese whey (CW) and wastewater, the anaerobic digestion (AD) process stands out as the most extensively studied technology (Valta et al., 2017). Although the COD and BOD concentrations of these wastewaters can vary significantly (Asunis et al., 2020), their typically warm and concentrated nature makes them highly suitable for anaerobic treatment (Demirel et al., 2005). Anaerobic digestion (AD) is an effective method for the treatment of cheese whey (CW), providing triple benefits: reduction of pollution load, energy production, and nutrient recovery (Kataki et al., 2016). In cases where dairy industry wastewater contains low suspended solids (SS) concentrations, anaerobic filter reactors are generally appropriate for biological treatment (Demirel et al., 2005). Cheese whey can be processed in anaerobic digestion systems for biogas production, during which methane gas is generated. Various anaerobic treatment technologies have demonstrated high efficiencies in removing COD from whey wastewater, with considerable methane production across different reactor configurations. The performance of different types of anaerobic reactors used for whey treatment is summarized in Table 1.

Table 1. Efficiency of anaerobic processes in treating whey

Reactor type	OLR (kg KOİ m ⁻³ day)	HRT (day)	COD Removal (%)	Methane production	Reference
UASB	2.4–13.5	3h 12h	95.6–96.3% 90–92%		Ramasamy et al., 2004
UASB	6.0	20	>85	0.33 (m ³ kg ⁻¹ COD)	Demirel et al., 2005
UASB	2-7.3	6	85-99		
Downflow fixed-film	13	4.9	75	0.28 m ³ kg ⁻¹ COD	Demirel et al., 2005
Two stage-CSTR		4	99	383 L biogas kg ⁻¹ COD _{removed}	Saddoud et al., 2007
Two stage-PABR		4.4	94	383 L CH ₄ kg ⁻¹ COD _{removed}	Antonopoulou et al., 2008
CSTR	3	2-4	80-95	280-380 L CH ₄ / COD _{removed}	Gannoun et al., 2008a
UAF		2	80-90	280 L CH ₄ / COD _{removed}	Gannoun et al., 2008b
Two stage-CSTR		20	95	134 L CH ₄ kg ⁻¹ COD _{removed}	Venetsaneas et al., 2009
Sequential Anaerobic	0.56 1.04 0.78	2 3 4	89 97 98		Frigon et al., 2009
Two stage UASB-CSTR	20		90	0.37 Nm ³ CH ₄ kg ⁻¹ COD	Diamantis et al., 2014
One stage-SBR		8.3	-	314.5 L CH ₄ kg ⁻¹ COD	Fernández et al., 2015
Two stage-SBR		12.5		340 L CH ₄ kg ⁻¹ COD	
Gradual UASB	19.4–28.7	1.3	94.7–95.1	6.4–9.5 m ³ CH ₄ day ⁻¹	Rico et al., 2015
EGBS		6-8	> 90	334 ve 328 mL CH ₄ g ⁻¹ COD	Cruz-Salomón et al., 2020
ABB			88.6	338.9 mL CH ₄ g ⁻¹ COD	Rincón-Catalán et al., 2022
TAR	0.416 kg VS l ⁻¹ day			565.8 L CH ₄ kg ⁻¹ VS	Ramos-Suárez et al., 2024
MEC-AD	2.1–3.3	310	98	0.75 L CH ₄ g ⁻¹ COD _{consumed}	Kanellos et al., 2025

UASB: upflow anaerobic sludge blanket; CSTR: continuously stirred tank reactor; MEC-AD: microbial electrolysis cell-anaerobic digestion; SBR: sequencing batch reactor; EGBS: expanded granular sludge bed reactor; TAR: Tubular anaerobic reactor; ABB: anaerobic batch bioreactor; UAF: upflow anaerobic filter

Upflow anaerobic sludge blanket (UASB) reactors achieved COD removal rates between 85% and 96.3% under organic loading rates (OLR) ranging from 2.4 to 13.5 kg COD m⁻³ day and hydraulic retention times (HRT) from 3 hours to 20 days, producing methane yields as high as 0.33 m³ kg⁻¹ COD. Fixed-film reactors and continuously stirred tank reactors (CSTRs) also performed effectively, with COD removals of 75% and up to 95%, respectively, and methane yields reaching 380 L CH₄ kg⁻¹ COD removed. Two-stage systems, including UASB-CSTR and CSTR-based combinations, consistently reported high COD removal (up to 99%) and methane yields of up to 383 L CH₄ kg⁻¹ COD removed. More advanced or hybrid systems such as expanded

granular sludge bed (EGBS), tubular anaerobic reactors (TAR), and microbial electrolysis cell-assisted anaerobic digestion (MEC-AD) exhibited both high COD removal efficiencies (>90–98%) and enhanced methane yields, with MEC-AD reaching 0.75 L CH₄ g⁻¹ COD consumed. Sequential anaerobic treatment also proved effective, with COD removal rates up to 98% depending on cycle duration. To enhance process stability and improve COD removal as well as CH₄ production, two-stage anaerobic digestion (AD) systems where the hydrolysis acetogenesis and methanogenesis phases are conducted in separate reactors have been proposed (Asunis et al., 2020). These findings demonstrate that cheese whey (CW) and dairy industry waste can be effectively

treated using anaerobic systems, and that their potential for energy production is significant. Anaerobic processes offer advantages not only in terms of organic matter removal, but also in renewable energy generation and sustainable waste management. However, variables such as system design, feeding rate, hydraulic retention time (HRT), and pre-treatment play a critical role in determining performance. Therefore, optimizing reactor types and operational conditions is essential for enhancing system efficiency.

2.2. Membrane technologies

In terms of organic composition, cheese whey (CW) primarily contains carbohydrates (4–5%, with lactose being the most abundant), proteins (0.6–0.8%), and lipids (0.4–0.5%) (Escalante et al., 2018). Due to its protein and peptide content, cheese whey (CW) is a significant source of bioactive compounds. However, the limited investment capacity of small- and medium-sized dairy enterprises prevents the valorization of a large portion of the CW produced globally (Pires et al., 2021). Membrane separation technology is an efficient method that stands out in water and industrial wastewater treatment due to its high efficiency, ease of scalability, and relatively low operational cost. It also contributes economically to the food, dairy, and pharmaceutical industries by enabling the recovery of valuable compounds such as lactose and proteins (Mansor et al., 2021). Membrane processes such as microfiltration, ultrafiltration, nanofiltration, and reverse osmosis are widely used to produce protein and lactose concentrates from cheese whey (CW) and secondary cheese whey (SCW), as well as for water recovery from whey (Valta et al., 2017; Talebi et al., 2020; Pires et al., 2021; Blais et al., 2022). Pressure-driven membrane filtration processes commonly used in the

dairy industry vary based on pore size and separation mechanism, such as sieving or diffusion (Mansor et al., 2021). Microfiltration (MF) has a pore size range of 0.02–4 μm and operates at low pressure. It is used for the removal of large particles such as fat globules and bacteria and is suitable for applications like casein enrichment. Ultrafiltration (UF) has smaller pores, ranging from 0.02 to 0.2 μm , and is used for concentrating proteins and in the production of protein isolates. It can also separate dissolved substances such as lactose and salts. Nanofiltration (NF), with extremely small pore sizes below 0.0002 μm , requires moderate pressure and allows partial passage of lactose and some ions. It is used for partial demineralization and to improve the quality of powdered products. Reverse osmosis (RO) is the membrane system with the smallest pore size and requires high pressure. It is used to concentrate milk and whey; however, due to the high viscosity of the feed, it carries a higher risk of membrane fouling. Each filtration type has a specific molecular weight cut-off and application purpose, offering distinct advantages and limitations in terms of process efficiency, product quality, and energy consumption, as summarized in Table 2. Compared to traditional separation techniques, membrane technologies provide notable environmental benefits such as decreased energy requirements, minimized wastewater production, and opportunities for water recovery and reuse. These systems can be easily integrated with other separation techniques and operate under moderate process conditions suitable for the food industry. Additionally, they do not require additives or solvents, and component separation occurs with high selectivity (Pires et al., 2021). Membrane technology stands out for its low energy demand, environmentally friendly nature, and selective separation capability.

Table 2. Comparison of membrane filtration methods used in milk and dairy products (Adapted from Pires et al., 2021; Blais et al., 2022)

Filtration type	Pore size (µm)	Operating pressure (MPa)	Molecular weight cut-off (kDa)	Applications	Benefits / Limitations
Microfiltration	0.02–4	0.03–0.2	100–500	Removal of fat globules, bacteria, and large protein aggregates	Used for casein enrichment and reduction of whey proteins
Ultrafiltration	0.02–0.2	0.1–1	1–100	Production of protein concentrates and isolates; milk and cheese standardization	Removes dissolved substances like lactose, salts, and vitamins; permeate can be used in lactose production
Nanofiltration	<0.0002	1–3	0.1–1	Concentration and partial demineralization; allows partial passage of lactose	Can remove 25–90% of monovalent ions; reduces hygroscopicity in powdered products; enhances lactose crystallization efficiency
Reverse Osmosis	<0.0002	3.5–10	<0.1	Concentration of milk or whey up to ~27% total solids content	Increased risk of membrane fouling due to high viscosity and osmotic pressure

The filtration process yields two distinct fractions: the retentate or concentrate, which contains molecules that cannot pass through the membrane, and the permeate or filtrate, which consists of molecules that do. The retentate of cheese whey (CW) includes proteins, fats, insoluble salts, lactose, and soluble minerals that are unable to pass through the membrane, while the permeate primarily contains lactose (Pires et al., 2021). Membrane processes such as microfiltration, ultrafiltration, nanofiltration, and reverse osmosis enable the separation of proteins, lactose, and minerals from cheese whey, contributing both to economic recovery and environmental impact reduction. However, the most common issues encountered in membrane operations are membrane fouling and concentration polarization. These problems lead to a decrease in permeation flux and changes in process selectivity. Minimizing such adverse effects is crucial, as they reduce both the permeate flow and membrane selectivity, and result in additional cleaning costs (Pires et al., 2021; Blais et al., 2022). Therefore, to achieve cost reduction through by-product recovery and minimize environmental impact, the application of ultrasound technology in cheese whey treatment has been proposed. In this context,

ultrasound-assisted cleaning has been reported to be an effective method for cleaning ultrafiltration membranes fouled with cheese whey protein concentrate, and thus can significantly contribute to improving overall process efficiency (Luján-Facundo et al., 2017).

3. Biotechnological potential of cheese whey (CW)

Modern approaches increasingly regard cheese whey (CW) not as a waste product but as a valuable biological resource with high added value. Due to its content of highly bioavailable proteins, lactose, and minerals, CW can be repurposed in various fields such as functional food ingredients, animal feed, probiotic production, and as a raw material for bioplastics (Smithers, 2008). In addition, the anaerobic degradability of CW offers opportunities for both biochemical methane potential and nutrient recovery, such as struvite precipitation (Escalante et al., 2018). Considered a versatile compound, struvite is commonly applied as a high-grade fertilizer, a fire-suppressing agent, and a sorbent in soil pollutant remediation (Yetilmezsoy et al., 2017). Furthermore, with appropriate fermentation techniques, CW can be used to produce eco-friendly products such as lactic

acid, ethanol, biogas, and polyhydroxyalkanoates (PHA). These biotechnological processes not only reduce organic pollution but also provide economically and environmentally sustainable solutions through the production of renewable energy and biomaterials (Chatzipaschali and Stamatis, 2012). Dark fermentation (DF) is a promising biotechnological approach for converting cheese whey (CW) into biohydrogen and volatile fatty acids (VFAs). Due to the high carbohydrate content of CW, this process can be carried out without the need for pretreatment or external inoculum. The hydrolysis of lactose into simple sugars is followed by its conversion into lactate, and subsequently into biohydrogen (H₂) and VFAs (Asunis et al., 2020). This provides both environmental and economic advantages in terms of energy generation and waste reduction. Cheese whey is also a suitable substrate for lactic acid fermentation, owing to its lactose and protein content. Lactic acid bacteria hydrolyze lactose into glucose and galactose, which are then converted into lactic acid. Depending on the fermentation conditions, either homolactic or heterolactic pathways can be followed. In fermentation processes using CW, strategies such as nutrient supplementation and product removal can enhance productivity. The products formed through CW fermentation, particularly volatile fatty acids (VFAs), can serve as precursors in biopolymer production. Biopolymers such as polylactic acid (PLA) and polyhydroxyalkanoates (PHAs) offer bio-based and biodegradable alternatives to fossil-derived plastics (Asunis et al., 2020). Microbial electrochemical technologies (METs) also provide potential for recovering energy from CW through microbial fuel cells (MFCs) to generate electricity, or through microbial electrolysis cells (MECs) to produce hydrogen (H₂) (Asunis et al., 2020; Antonopoulou et al., 2021). In addition, the combination of acidic pH shifting with ultrasound has been identified as an effective method to enhance the emulsifying properties of whey protein isolate (WPI). WPI treated with acidic pH shifting and ultrasound shows

potential for use in the food industry in the development of novel and effective emulsifiers (Jiang et al., 2022).

4. Conclusion

Cheese whey (CW) is recognized as both an environmentally significant waste product and a by-product with substantial economic and biotechnological potential in the dairy sector. This study has holistically examined CW's composition, currently applied treatment methods and opportunities for its biotechnological utilization. Notably, enhanced treatment approaches such as anaerobic digestion and membrane-based systems have demonstrated strong potential in reducing CW's organic load, while also enabling energy generation and the recovery of valuable compounds. In addition, the application of ultrasound in membrane cleaning has emerged as a promising method to reduce chemical usage, contributing to both economic efficiency and environmental sustainability. Biotechnological strategies that convert CW into high-value products such as lactic acid, bioplastics, and biogas are considered effective tools aligned with circular economy practices. Effectively valorizing CW is therefore essential, not only to mitigate its environmental burden but also to create economic benefit. Integrating CW into recovery-based treatment systems supports the development of sustainable food production and reinforces environmental protection efforts. Ultimately, converting CW from a problematic waste stream into a valuable bioresource highlights the importance of further studies in this field.

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